

Some factors that favor its buildup are becoming more prevalent with improved cultivation practices. They include:

- 1) intensive cultivation of rice (e.g., double-cropping, triple-cropping, growing of 5 crops in 2 years);
- 2) large-scale planting of high yielding, high-tillering and nitrogen-responsive hopper-susceptible varieties such as Bahagia, Jaya, Mat Candu, and Seri Sekinchan;
- 3) close spacing between rice plants (e.g., 20 cm in parts of Sekinchan);
- 4) staggered or continuous cropping;

5) use of excessive fertilizers, particularly high rates of nitrogen; and 6) intensive and indiscriminate use of broad-spectrum insecticides.

Among the major researches currently undertaken are 1) more comprehensive studies of the biology and ecology of the planthopper under local conditions; 2) evaluation and screening for resistant varieties; 3) developing a surveillance and monitoring system to provide early detection so that appropriate and timely control measures

may be taken; 4) evaluation of intensive light trapping for control; 5) investigation of cultural aspects relating to planthopper development; 6) studies of the role and optimal employment of natural enemies; and 7) investigations of the efficient and judicious use of pesticides. ❧

Infestations of rice planthoppers observed or reported in Malaysia.

Year	Location	Planthopper	Remarks
1925	Perak (Krian)	<i>Sogatella</i> sp.	—
1929	Perak (Krian)	<i>Sogatella</i> sp.	—
	Province Wellesley	<i>Sogatella</i> sp.	—
1967	Trengganu	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> and <i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	More than 6,000 ha affected. Extensive and severe hopperburn
1968	Perlis	—	Hopperburn in small patches
	Kedah	—	”
	Perak	—	”
	Province Wellesley (Bukit Merah)	—	”
	Province Wellesley (Bumbong Lima)	—	”
1974	Province Wellesley (Sungai Sintok)	—	”
1975	Province Wellesley (Bumbong Lima)	<i>N. lugens</i> and <i>S. furcifera</i>	”
	Province Wellesley (Pinang Tunggal)		”
1976	Province Wellesley (Pinang Tunggal)		”
	Kedah (several localities)	—	”
	Negri Sembilan	—	”
	Selangor (Tanjong Karang)	—	”
1977	Selangor (Tanjong Karang)	<i>N. lugens</i>	Severe hopperburn in several localities. Affected area estimated to be more than 400 ha
1977	Malacca	—	General yellowing with heavy infestations
1977	Negri Sembilan	—	”
1917	Perak (Langkap)	<i>N. lugens</i>	”
1977	Perak (S. Manek, Parit, & Krian)	<i>N. lugens</i>	Heavy infestations
1977	Province Wellesley (Pinang Tunggal)	<i>N. lugens</i>	Hopperburn in small patches over an area of about 7 ha

Rapid reduction of brown planthoppers by intensive light trapping during an outbreak in Malaysia

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Light traps were observed to attract high populations of brown planthoppers (**BPH**) during a 1967 outbreak that affected about 6,000 ha of rice in Trengganu, Malaysia. Scientists then speculated that light traps might be used to control **BPH**. The **BPH** again showed strong phototropic response in a 1977 outbreak, in which about 15,000 ha was infested in Tanjong Karang. Depending on the natural infestations, as many as 92.16 million **BPH** (131 kg; 1 g = about 705 **BPH**) may be caught by 15 fluorescent lamp traps in 4% hours (1900–2330). Most insects were generally caught during the early evening hours. In one study, the catches per trap were 17,767 **BPH** from 1930 to 2030 hours, 1,531 from 2030 to 2130 hours, 4,389 from 2130 to 2230 hours, and 7,047 from 2230–2330 hours.

The enormous catches stimulated a study of the possibility of intensive light trapping to reduce **BPH** populations during an outbreak. In one study, 20 traps (using pressure gas lamps) were spaced around a 120-ha field from 1830 to 2300 hours. On 320 randomly selected hills (covering 32 sample points), the **BPH** population was reduced from 397 macropterous **BPH**/hill before light trapping to 156 macropterous **BPH**/hill after trapping (see table). In another study 47, 42, and 41 pressure lamp traps were used on 3 successive nights between 1900 and 2230 hours in a 100-ha field. Unlike in the earlier study, these traps were evenly spaced over the entire field.

Effect of intensive light trapping^a on the rice brown planthopper during an outbreak in Sg. Burong, Tanjung Karang, Malaysia.

Planthopper count	Planthoppers/hill (no.)		
	Macropterous adults	Brachypterous adults	Nymphs
Before light trapping ^b	397	367	174
After light trapping	156	12	492

^aTwenty pressure lamp traps were placed around the infested field between 1830 and 2300 hours.

^bAug. 2, 1977.

Population counts of the BPH over 140 randomly selected hills covering 14 sample points showed that the BPH population declined drastically soon after the light trapping (see figure). The

Change in brown planthopper population in localities with intensive light trapping (Sg. Leman) and without light traps (Sawah Sempadan and Sg. Burong). Arrow and number above indicate, respectively, the night and number of light traps in operation.

Outbreak of Malayan black rice bug in Nellore district

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A sudden outbreak of Malayan black rice bug *Scotinophara coarctata* was noted in the last week of May 1977 in Nellore district, Andhra Pradesh. The bug had earlier been reported to damage rice crops

total catches for the three successive nights were 2.88, 3.42, and 4.29 million BPH, respectively. The fact that only the macropterous adults were generally caught (see table) accounted for the residual population observed in the figure.

For comparison, the populations of BPH were measured for the same periods at two other localities, Sawah Sempadan and Sg. Burong, where light trapping was not used. In these areas, the population was not significantly reduced (see figure).

The findings show that intensive light trapping could rapidly remove large BPH populations in an outbreak. Theoretically, one light trap/0.4 ha (1 trap/acre) might remove as many as 141 BPH/hill, or even more if the efficiency of the traps could be increased. The lowering of a BPH population before insecticide control may prove critical, as chemicals generally are not effective enough to prevent hopperburn during outbreaks.

Although intensive light trapping might play an important role, its use as the sole means of control still requires further investigation. Success seems possible only if the BPH population is composed mostly of the macropterous adults.

in other parts of India. In 150 ha of rabi paddy, infestation was severe in CO 29 and IET 2508 varieties at the time of flowering. Yield losses of from 60 to 85% were recorded. The bugs also seriously damaged almost 100 ha of IET 2508 in the transplanted early kharif crop. They seemed to prefer young seedlings; in some places, nurseries of CO 29 and IET 2508 were almost totally destroyed. Irrigation water was standing in the affected plots although the weather was mostly dry. In heavily infested plots, about 200 bugs/hill were

Outbreak of *Heteronychus oryzae* in rice seedlings near Rokupr, Sierra Leone

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During early June 1977, an outbreak of *Heteronychus oryzae* occurred at Magbolontor, near a mangrove swamp where extensive rice experimental trials are conducted by the Rice Research Station, Rokupr.

All the experimental fields and nurseries at Magbolontor had been direct-seeded at about the end of May. At about the two-leaf stage, glossy dark-brown beetles (*Heteronychus oryzae*) began to attack the rice seedlings.

Damage to rice seedlings by *Heteronychus oryzae* at Magbolontor, Sierra Leone, 8 June 1977.

Variety	Seedling infestation (%)
2526	1.7
Huallaga	4.2
052/37	4.5
Ngovie	5.5
Bakutu	6.3
Parmatis	8.0
Gissi 27	8.1
Andy 301	9.2
ROK 4	12.8
Adny 4	29.9
Sokopent	33.8
Babadin	45.5
Gbinteh	49.5
Pa Panel	51.0
M-207	52.0
ROK 3	72.6 ^a
BD 2	87.5
Mahsuri	94.5

^aSample unit was 1 sq m. Twenty sample units were taken in 1.4-ha seed multiplication fields, and two sample units were recorded from each plot of the other varieties for varietal observation experiments.

found, mostly at the base of the plant. Surprisingly, not a single bug was found in the dry nurseries. Farmers were advised to spray dieldrin, gamma BHC, methyl parathion, malathion, or dichlorvos. Less expensive chemicals such as DDT or BHC, either as dust or spray, have been found equally effective.